

**THE INFLUENCE OF RESIN SYSTEM, CURE
AND POSTCURE ON THE MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE
OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED POLYESTERS**

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It is often said that resin properties have little significant effect on the mechanical performance of reinforced polyesters due to the dominating strength and stiffness of the reinforcement. This point of view, coupled with the vagueness of standards on conditions of cure, has led to a continuing debate on the influence of resin properties on laminate properties.

On the one hand, advocates of high catalyst content, high workshop temperature and the need for postcure insist that this is the only way to produce well cured material. Indeed, a number of specifiers and end users have attempted to incorporate workshop environmental conditions, 'degree of cure' and its measurement into their documents without considering the implications. Others, perhaps less interested in the search for a sound data base, pay minimal attention to the possible variation between "design" properties and properties achievable under workshop conditions, leaving recommendations on cure solely to the resin and catalyst suppliers. In contrast, there are those who maintain that improvements, above certain minimum levels, in the properties of the resin matrix have no measurable effects on laminate performance except under certain circumstances. A particular case in point being when the laminate is in contact with aggressive chemical environments where the selection of a chemical-resistant resin is regarded as over-riding.

This paper attempts to place a few popular misconceptions into perspective by considering the range of possible effects cure and postcure can have on cast resin and laminate properties, paying particular attention to gelcoat performance. Recent data on a series of gelcoated glass chopped strand mat/polyester laminates is presented to show how certain combinations of materials can result in unacceptable performance. From examination of actual structures and laboratory test data, it is evident that laminate performance can be very dependent on the level of postcure and that often, the potential afforded by using highly cross-linkable resins is not attained because inappropriate postcure schedules are used. This is particularly important for GRP components and structures operating at elevated temperatures where the use of high heat distortion point material, which generally means high cross-link density in thermosetting resins, is essential to provide resistance to medium/long term deformation.

Due consideration is given to the balance between various mechanical properties and the need to be aware of the damaging effects improvements in some properties can have on others. For example, laminate modulus may be increased by postcure, but this has an associated reduction in elongation to failure as a result of improved cross-linking in the resin matrix. At worst, such problems are unknown to both designer and fabricator, and may only manifest themselves later when the component has failed prematurely in service.

It is concluded that for a given application, there is much greater scope for optimising resin, reinforcement and curing systems than is generally realised. While it is emphasised that care and control over cure and postcure should be exercised by fabricators, concern is expressed about misleading "blanket" statements on the necessity to postcure, at all costs, at elevated temperatures in order to render GRP a useful structural material.

THE CURING CYCLE

Unsaturated polyesters are generally cured at room temperatures by a free radical copolymerisation reaction using catalysts (initiators) activated by accelerators (promoters) or by the use of a suitable catalyst and moderate heating.

Although the term "catalyst" has entered everyday usage in the GRP industry, it is something of a misnomer. Catalysts for polyesters are typically organic peroxides and do not speed up the chemical reaction whilst themselves remaining unchanged. They necessarily decompose to initiate the reaction and because of their hazardous nature, they must be supplied as a paste or liquid dispersion in a plasticiser, or as a powder in an inert filler.

Accelerators are active compounds such as cobalt octoate and tertiary amines. Since only small additions are necessary, they are normally diluted to various concentrations in a solvent for easy dispersion in the resin. Sometimes dual promoters are preferred and in recent years, resins have been supplied in pre-accelerated form.

Curing is a multi-stage reaction. By selecting resins and curing agents and controlling their relative amounts, the system can be tailored to meet specific processing requirements. All polyester resins contain an inhibitor/stabiliser to adjust the geltime and give adequate shelf life. Immediately after addition of the catalyst to the resin it starts to react with the inhibitor. Using a catalyst alone, the inhibitor is used up rather slowly and the resin will have a pot life of many hours. In the presence of an accelerator or under heat, the polymerisation reaction is speeded up but the resin is still workable. During this so-called "induction" period the reinforcement can be impregnated with resin and consolidated until it begins to gel. At this point, cross-linking takes place accompanied by heat evolution due to exotherm. Finally, the resin hardens - quickly at first, but in some cases hardening can continue over a few days or even weeks. Postcuring at elevated temperatures shortens the time to reach full maturity.

STANDARDS, SPECIFICATIONS AND CODES OF PRACTICE

A structural material must exhibit several characteristics. It must have sufficient mechanical strength and stiffness; resistance to fatigue, impact, creep and environmental attack; and often appearance, fire resistance, and easy cleaning are further requirements. Sometimes two materials can be combined: one to provide the mechanical properties and the other in the form of a protective cladding or lining. GRP can meet both of these - it can be used alone as the material of construction or as a lining for metallic materials, or it can be utilised to reinforce other materials, usually thermoplastics. This paper deals mainly with short term mechanical properties but it is worth briefly reviewing two attributes of GRP which have attracted design engineers in a wide range of industries:

1. GRP laminates in contact with foodstuffs must satisfy certain requirements regarding the chemicals used in manufacture of the resin and curing agents and/or it must be demonstrated that residual volatiles in the finished component are below a prescribed level. For example, the American and German Regulations (1,2) contain a "positive" list of approved raw materials which have been proven not to be a health hazard whereas a somewhat different approach by the British Plastics Federation (3) is based on food-grade resins which produce an acceptable low-taint laminate of total residual volatiles content below 0.1% by weight.
2. Tanks, vessels, pipes and other items of process equipment represent some of the most demanding applications for GRP. A number of resin types are available and the best chemical/corrosion resistance is achieved using a carefully constructed resin-rich "barrier layer" in contact with the aggressive environment. Degradation is slow in polyester laminates and usually characterised by loss of properties but no matter how chemical-resistant the resin in the controlled conditions of the laboratory, long term performance in service is very dependent on the degree of cross-linking, ie. cure.

The general consensus of opinion, supported by substantial test work and practical experience, is in favour of "controlled" cure for all GRP applications; and for critical applications where an inert surface is highly desirable, postcure is essential. The questions are at what temperature, for how long and how should cure be measured?

Scott Bader's Technical Leaflet No 164 for Crystic 491PA, a pre-accelerated isophthalic polyester resin (HDT = 75°C) for low-taint and chemical-resistant mouldings, offers very useful advice:

"After release from the mould, laminates should be allowed to mature for 24 hours at workshop temperature (20°C). They should then be postcured for 3 hours at 80°C or 15 hours at 50°C. When laminates are required to withstand temperatures between 50 and 80°C in service, the postcuring temperature should always be at least as high as that which the laminate is required to operate. The postcure is most effective if it is carried out immediately after the 24 hour maturing period".

British Standard 4994:1973 Section 2.2.2.1 requires the determination of a part factor K_5 relating to curing properties. In many ways it imposes a penalty on fabricators who do not postcure:

"Where the vessel is subjected to a complete curing procedure, including a full postcure at elevated temperature at the manufacturer's works the part factor K_5 shall be taken as 1.1. For all other curing procedures, the part factor K_5 shall be 1.5. However, in the case of resin having a heat distortion temperature (HDT) of 70°C or less, factor K_5 may be taken as 1.3 provided that the HDT achieved by the curing procedure adopted is at least 20°C above the design temperature of the vessel".

Lloyds approval procedure for polyester resins places the responsibility for selecting curing agents and addition levels firmly on the resin manufacturer but has the following to say about curing schedule:

"Tests are to be conducted on resin castings and on chopped strand mat laminates produced at an initial cure of 24 hours at 16-20°C, followed by a postcure period of not longer than 16 hours at a temperature not exceeding 40°C".

Standards and Codes of Practice frequently mention surface hardness and degree of cure, and almost always refer designers to the recommendations of resin suppliers.

PS 15:1969 Section 3.3.7.1 states "The laminate shall have a Barcol Hardness (to ASTM D2583) of at least 90 per cent of the resin manufacturer's minimum specified hardness for the cured resin"

An Oil Company Specification for GRP tank linings states "The cure of resin linings shall be tested by locally swabbing the resin surface with solvent. Methyl ethyl ketone (MEK) shall be used for epoxy, and acetone for polyester linings. Softening or tackiness of the surface is an indication of improper cure".

Assessment of the degree of cure is an important stage in laminate inspection. Severe undercure is relatively easy to detect - the laminate will be spongy and emit a dull sound when tapped with a coin. Slight undercure is less easy to establish, especially if it is patchy over large surfaces. Under these circumstances, it may be possible to apply a few drops of acetone to the laminate surface and inspect for signs of softening or tackiness. A further, more convenient workshop quality control method is to use a Barcol Impressor. Barcol hardness is not an absolute measurement of degree of cure but it can differentiate between an acceptable laminate having a Barcol figure of say 35-40 and a really poor laminate below 25. It should be noted, however, that whilst surface hardness readings on cast resins may prove fairly consistent, readings on laminates can show considerable scatter due to the presence of fillers and reinforcement.

For low-taint applications degree of cure is usually defined by the residual volatiles content, as measured by titrimetric or gas-liquid chromatographic methods. For many years specifications have emphasised residual styrene content and to a lesser extent, benzaldehyde. This has proved satisfactory for GRP wine tanks, potable water pipelines, container panels etc but there are signs that in future, further attention will be paid to other residual volatiles and impurities from the curing agents.

Curing at ambient temperatures results in fairly high residual styrene content (up to 5%) for most resins and curing systems. The lowest levels being synonymous with high catalyst and accelerator additions. Postcuring at elevated temperatures can reduce the residual styrene content by an order of magnitude but careful thought must be given to the choice of curing system and the relative additions. Roskott et al (4,5) have presented interesting properties contour diagrams for a high reactivity orthophthalic resin, showing the dangers of generalising about catalyst and accelerator types, addition levels and postcuring schedules for minimal residual styrene content. They pointed out that with postcured MEKP/cobalt systems, low residual styrene can be achieved by increasing the addition level of each, whereas BPO/DMA systems are more sensitive to changes in the BPO level than the DMA. Further, the authors recommend that there is an advantage in selecting a short postcure time at a temperature level above the heat deflection temperature of the resin in preference to prolonged postcure at lower temperatures.

Recent work at Scott Bader supports the comments by Roskott and further investigations have been carried out to identify other residual volatiles associated with various combinations of resin type and curing agents. For example, Table 2 compares the residual volatiles in bisphenol polyester laminates for two diverse curing systems. The cumene hydroperoxide/vanadium system exhibits reduced residual styrene, even before high temperature postcure, but there are substantial concentrations of residual cumene, xylene and diacetone alcohol which are not present with the MEKP/cobalt system. Further curing problems arise with bisphenol resins in contact with foodstuffs due to their high initial styrene monomer content (up to 50% by wt). Vinyl ester resins also suffer the same limitations (6). In no way does the difficulty in reducing the residual styrene level in bisphenol and vinyl ester resins detract from their obvious advantages in many other applications. The high level of chemical resistance afforded by such resins seldom justifies their selection for foodstuff applications, except under elevated temperature service conditions. Most food grade applications are adequately covered by the use of orthophthalic and isophthalic acid based resin. They contain lower levels of styrene monomer, are less expensive, and more easily meet the appropriate Regulations using postcure conditions which are less intense than those necessary to approach an acceptable level of residual volatiles with bisphenol and vinyl ester resins.

CURE AND POSTCURE

CAST PROPERTIES

The factors affecting cure of polyester resins are:

- i) Resin type
- ii) Resin reactivity
- iii) Cure system and initial cure
- iv) Postcure schedule.

The most commonly used catalyst/accelerator systems for curing polyester resins do not significantly affect cast resin properties providing they are used in sufficient quantities to ensure good initial cure - too little means permanent undercure (Barcol hardness below 25) which is irretrievable whatever the postcure schedule; too much means uncontrollable exotherm and "burn-up" resulting in unacceptable appearance, cracking, distortion etc.

High temperature postcure has several desirable effects, by increasing cross-link density, ie. by reducing the level of residual unsaturation in the cured system:

- i) increased Barcol Hardness
- ii) increased Heat Deflection Temperature
(see Figure 1 and Table 1)
- iii) increased stiffness (modulus)
- iv) improved chemical resistance.

However, postcure reduces flexibility (see Figure 2) and ultimate tensile strength.

As shown in Figure 1, high reactivity resins are affected more by postcure than those of lower reactivity. In fact the optimum properties of high reactivity resins are only achieved with high temperature postcure, often at the expense of properties like flexibility as shown in Figure 2. Here it can be seen that low reactivity resins generally remain fairly flexible after high temperature postcure, although this is not always the case with orthophthalic acid based resins where the glycol types used in their manufacture often exhibit more dominating effects on flexibility than in the case of isophthalic acid based resins.

LAMINATE PROPERTIES

The presence of reinforcement tends to somewhat obscure the effects of cure and postcure observed on cast resins. Nevertheless, it is possible to see marked changes in laminate modulus, flexibility, strain to first damage (see Table 1 and Tables 3a, 3b) and chemical resistance when high temperature postcure is applied.

If optimum operating performance in chemical environments and maximum stiffness are required from GRP then there is a need for high temperature postcure. This is clear from Tables 3a and 3b where for a given resin type, range of reactivities and curing conditions, the following important factors emerge:

- i) No significant effect of resin reactivity on ultimate tensile strength of chopped strand mat (CSM) laminates for each cure system under room temperature postcure conditions. A marginal reduction in laminate tensile strength is observed between low and high reactivity resins of the same generic type when high temperature postcure is applied.
- ii) Significant changes occur in tensile modulus of CSM laminates as postcure temperature is increased; this occurs as a result of increased rigidity in the resin as it becomes more highly cross-linked - important to the designer because GRP structures are invariably designed according to stiffness criteria.
- iii) Tensile elongation to failure of CSM laminates decreases as a result of high temperature postcure.
- iv) The application of acoustic emission techniques as a tool for assessing onset of microdamage indicates marked reductions in the level of strain to onset of first damage in CSM laminates which have been postcured at elevated temperatures. Again, designers should be aware of this phenomenon where high reactivity resins are to be used.

GELCOAT PROPERTIES

It is also enlightening to note the effect of high temperature postcure on gelcoats (flowcoats). In Table 4 it is clear that high temperature postcure reduces the strain to failure of gelcoats backed up with CSM laminates. It is also apparent that the type of resin used in the back-up laminate can have a significant effect on gelcoat strain to failure. Figure 3 shows both the effects

of gelcoat flexibility and resin flexibility on the gelcoat strain to failure of CSM laminates under flexural conditions. This data was first reported several years ago (7) and shows how important it is to carefully consider combinations of gelcoat and back-up resin system for optimum gelcoat performance.

More recent work is summarised in Figures 4 and 5 where the effects of gelcoat flexibility and back-up resin flexibility on the gelcoat strain to failure of CSM laminates are shown under tensile conditions. It is obvious from the data that the following guidelines should be followed to achieve the best mechanical performance of gelcoats and flowcoats, especially after high temperature postcure:

- i) Use the same gelcoat and back-up resin system throughout ie. a "matched" system. In many applications expensive gelcoats are unnecessarily used with less expensive back-up resin systems. Indeed there are sound chemical and mechanical reasons for using the same resin system throughout construction, thereby avoiding potential interfacial difficulties.
- ii) Use the most flexible* gelcoat (flowcoat) possible but care must be taken that this is not at the expense of chemical resistance.
- iii) Use the most flexible back-up resin consistent with the desired mechanical performance.

Incipient failures have been observed in both room temperature and high temperature postcured systems, eg. a boat hull made using a very brittle back-up resin (1.5% elongation) and a flexible gelcoat (3.5% elongation) exhibited extensive gelcoat cracking in the vicinity of frames and stiffeners. This problem was eliminated by switching to a back-up resin with an elongation of 2.5%.

A further example involving a large item of process equipment, postcured at 80°C for several hours, suffered similar premature gelcoat failure under handling loads. In this case the back-up resin was a high reactivity isophthalic acid based system (2.0% elongation) with a bisphenol resin flowcoat (3.5% elongation). It was interesting to discover that without postcure, tensile elongations of 3.3% and 5.7% respectively were recorded for these resin systems, ie. an almost proportionate upward shift in each resin. No handling difficulties were experienced with the equipment prior to high temperature postcure but this was necessary to achieve the required degree of chemical resistance. It would seem that mismatch in itself is not always a problem providing that the flexibilities of the two systems are sufficiently high. Clearly, compromises have been found between chemical and mechanical performance of gelcoat and back-up resin systems to ensure more than adequate "in-service" life for many items of GRP process equipment. One means of achieving this is to use a barrier layer (8) incorporating a surface veil and several millimeters of high resin content CSM laminate, constructed with the same resin, before the structural laminate is laid up using an alternative resin system for economic reasons.

* We define flexibility in terms of tensile elongation to failure. Typically 2-6% is considered flexible for commercially available systems - below 2% being considered as brittle. It should be recognised that flexibility is not necessarily synonymous with toughness in composite materials.

Since maximum chemical resistance is only afforded by polyester resins when they are fully cross-linked by high temperature postcure, an alternative approach is often taken for the more corrosive environments, i.e. the use of thermoplastic liners. The thermoplastic provides the environmental barrier and the backing structural GRP laminate only requires a moderate degree of postcure to enable it to perform satisfactorily at the required operating temperature. Since GRP behind thermoplastic liners is operating in an air environment, postcure at high temperatures is only really necessary if long term deformation is likely to be a possible problem. Indeed, for many GRP applications the need to postcure at elevated temperatures should be a secondary consideration providing the material is sufficiently well cured to give the desired structural performance with more thought being given to the retention of useful properties such as flexibility and toughness. Having said this, it must be stressed again that under no circumstances is it advised that GRP liners in contact with aggressive chemicals should forego postcure at elevated temperatures.

If high temperature postcure is necessary then thorough cure must be achieved throughout the laminate thickness. This is best carried out in controlled air circulation ovens. Infra red lamps, hot air fans and boil-out are second best, giving a degree of postcure to the surface in contact with the environment rather than to the bulk laminate.

An additional source of confusion and worry is the use of flexibilising resins to toughen chemically-resistant systems. There is no doubt that sufficient additions of flexibilising resin increase the tensile elongation to failure of cast resin (see Table 5) but this is often at the expense of other important properties such as heat distortion temperature, modulus and especially chemical resistance.

CONCLUSIONS

The vagueness of Standards on the subject of cure is not surprising. GRP is a versatile material and the possible combinations of reinforcements, resins, curing agents, fillers etc is almost infinite. By selecting some of the more popular systems we have reduced the number of variables and attempted to show the trade-off in properties as complete cure is approached.

It is important for the fabricator to achieve the "design" properties as specified by the design engineer. If these are inconsistent or the environment is loosely defined, nonsense is made of design factors on the short term properties and it is anyone's guess as to the "safety" factors towards the end of service life.

The work reported in this paper has concentrated on the influence of resin system, cure and postcure on short-term properties. Similar effects can be expected on long-term static and dynamic properties - some are likely to be enhanced by postcure but as yet, we have not verified which properties and to what degree.

The following main points are summarised:

1. It is recommended that consideration be given to using the same resin system throughout construction, especially where postcure is a requirement.
2. Gelcoat performance is a function of both gelcoat and back-up resin flexibility. In general, the greater the flexibilities and the closer they are matched, the less the risk of premature gelcoat failure.

3. With commercially available polyester resins, postcure improves modulus and chemical resistance but at the expense of flexibility. Clearly, this does not seriously limit the usefulness of GRP in demanding applications providing it is recognised at the design stage.
4. For low-taint applications, further attention should be paid to curing systems and their associated residual volatiles. Postcure will generally reduce these to an acceptable level.

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FIGURE 1 THE EFFECT OF POSTCURE SCHEDULE ON THE HEAT DISTORTION TEMPERATURE OF THREE CAST POLYESTER RESIN SYSTEMS

Cure: 2% Medium Reactivity MEKP

1% of 0.45% Cobalt Solution

FIGURE 2 THE EFFECT OF POSTCURE SCHEDULE ON THE TENSILE ELONGATION TO FAILURE OF THREE CAST POLYESTER RESIN SYSTEMS

- Low Reactivity Orthophthalic Acid Based Resin
- Medium Reactivity Isophthalic Acid Based Resin
- High Reactivity Isophthalic Acid Based Resin

FIGURE 3 EFFECT OF ELONGATION AT BREAK OF THE BACKING RESIN ON GELCOAT STRAIN TO FAILURE IN FLEXURE

(4 x 450 g/m² CSM laminates - 30% glass by wt)

Postcure: 24/3 hrs RT/80°C

FIGURE 4 EFFECT OF ELONGATION AT BREAK OF THE BACKING RESIN ON GELCOAT STRAIN TO FAILURE IN TENSION
(4 x 450 g/m² CSM laminates - 30% glass by weight)
Postcure: 28 days room temperature (RT)

Tensile Elongation at Break of the Gelcoat in Cast Form (%)

FIGURE 5. EFFECT OF ELONGATION AT BREAK OF THE BACKING RESIN ON GELCOAT STRAIN TO FAILURE IN TENSION

(4 x 450 g/m² CSM laminates - 30% glass by weight)

Postcure: 24/3 hrs RT/80°C

Postcure Schedule	7 days RT	24/16 hrs RT/40°C	24/5/3 hrs RT/80/120°C
Property			
CAST RESIN			
Tensile Elongation to Failure (%)	5.7	5.5	3.5
Heat Deflection Temperature (°C)	59	65	120
CSM LAMINATE (30% glass by wt)			
Flexural Strength (MPa)	138	157	150
Flexural Modulus (GPa)	5.7	6.4	7.8

TABLE 1 THE EFFECT OF POSTCURE ON THE PROPERTIES OF BISPHENOL RESIN CASTINGS AND LAMINATES

Cure: 2% Medium Reactivity MEKP
6% of 1% Cobalt Solution

Cure System	Postcure Schedule	Residual Volatiles (% w/w)					
		Styrene	Cumene & Xylenes	Toluene	Benzaldehyde	Diacetone Alcohol	Total
2% medium reactivity MEKP + 6% of 1% Cobalt Solution	48hrs RT	1	0.03	-	0.09	0.005	1
	28 days RT	1.1	-	-	-	-	-
	24/16hrs RT/60°C	0.75	-	-	-	-	-
	24/3hrs RT/80°C	0.65	-	-	-	-	-
	24/2hrs RT/100°C	0.12	-	-	-	-	-
	24/2hrs RT/120°C	0.04	0.02	0.005	0.08	0.005	0.15
2% Cumene Hydroperoxide + 1% Promoter BS + 1% Vanadium Compound	48hrs RT	0.6	0.3	-	0.03	0.35	1
	28 days RT	0.6	-	-	-	-	-
	24/16hrs RT/60°C	0.15	-	-	-	-	-
	24/3hrs RT/80°C	0.03	-	-	-	-	-
	24/2hrs RT/100°C	0.005	-	-	-	-	-
	24/2hrs RT/120°C	0.005	0.2	0.01	0.015	0.32	0.55

TABLE 2 THE EFFECT OF CURING CONDITIONS ON THE RESIDUAL VOLATILE CONTENT OF CHOPPED STRAND MAT REINFORCED BISPHENOL RESIN LAMINATES

Example of abbreviation used to describe postcure schedule:

24/16 hrs RT/60°C = 24 hrs at room temperature followed by a further 16 hrs in an oven at 60°C

Cure	Cure A					Cure B				
Resin Type	Orthophthalic			Isophthalic		Orthophthalic			Isophthalic	
Reactivity Property	Low	Medium	High	Low	High	Low	Medium	High	Low	High
Tensile Strength (MPa)	110	98	104	99	96	104	99	102	104	100
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	7.1	6.6	6.7	6.5	7.4	6.9	6.9	6.4	6.3	6.2
Tensile Elongation to Failure (%)	1.9	1.7	1.8	2.0	1.6	1.9	1.8	1.9	2.0	2.0
Stress To First Noise (MPa)	110	93	104	99	93	102	96	90	104	100
Strain To First Noise (%)	1.9	1.7	1.8	2.0	1.5	1.8	1.8	1.7	2.0	2.0
Flexural Strength (MPa)	184	178	171	198	179	185	183	157	176	175
Flexural Modulus (GPa)	5.5	6.1	5.2	5.6	6.4	5.9	6.3	5.6	5.7	5.3
Compression Strength (MPa)	169	186	162	170	197	165	177	155	150	190
Compression Modulus (GPa)	8.7	8.1	6.5	7.0	8.0	6.7	7.2	5.8	6.3	6.2

TABLE 3 THE EFFECT OF POSTCURE ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CHOPPED STRAND MAT LAMINATES

- (a) Postcure: 28 days room temperature (RT)
 Glass Content: 30% by wt (4 x 450 g/m²)
 Cure A: 2% medium reactivity MEKP + 1% of 0.45% Cobalt solution
 Cure B: 2% low reactivity MEKP + 1% of 0.45% Cobalt solution

Cure	Cure A					Cure B				
Resin Type	Orthophthalic			Isophthalic		Orthophthalic			Isophthalic	
Reactivity Property	Low	Medium	High	Low	High	Low	Medium	High	Low	High
Tensile Strength (MPa)	96	86	82	90	80	97	82	79	91	82
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	7.4	8.2	8.2	7.7	8.3	7.0	7.4	7.6	7.2	8.6
Tensile Elongation to Failure (%)	1.7	1.2	1.4	1.4	1.2	1.6	1.3	1.5	1.4	1.3
Stress to First Noise (MPa)	80	53	50	78	49	80	55	46	77	48
Strain to First Noise (%)	1.3	0.7	0.6	1.2	0.6	1.3	0.8	0.6	1.2	0.6
Flexural Strength (MPa)	183	181	172	156	168	184	161	162	166	169
Flexural Modulus (GPa)	6.9	8.5	6.4	6.0	6.7	7.0	6.9	7.3	6.7	7.2
Compressive Strength (MPa)	160	199	175	181	186	157	185	170	185	194
Compressive Modulus (GPa)	7.9	7.7	8.6	8.4	8.3	7.4	7.4	7.9	7.2	7.0

TABLE 3 THE EFFECT OF POSTCURE ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CHOPPED STRAND MAT LAMINATES

- (b) Postcure: 24 hrs at RT, followed by 5 hrs at 80°C, followed by 3 hrs at 120°C
 Glass Content: 30% by wt (4 x 450 g/m²)
 Cure A: 2% medium reactivity MEKP + 1% of 0.45% Cobalt solution
 Cure B: 2% low reactivity MEKP + 1% of 0.45% Cobalt solution

Gelcoat	Bisphenol Resin				Vinyl Ester Resin			
Back-up Resin	Low Reactivity Isophthalic	High Reactivity Isophthalic	Bisphenol	Vinyl Ester	Low Reactivity Isophthalic	High Reactivity Isophthalic	Bisphenol	Vinyl Ester
Property								
Postcure: 24/16 hrs RT/40°C								
Tensile Elongation to Failure (%)	2.37	1.75	1.83	2.26	2.05	1.72	1.78	2.07
Gelcoat Strain to Failure (%)	2.37	1.45	1.65	2.24	2.05	1.63	1.44	2.07
Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	110	85	90	92	100	75	82	90
Stress to Gelcoat Failure (MPa)	110	70	84	90	100	69	73	90
Postcure: 24/3 hrs RT/80°C								
Tensile Elongation to Failure (%)	1.95	1.74	1.48	1.60	1.78	1.78	1.49	1.64
Gelcoat Strain to Failure (%)	1.56	0.71	1.00	1.21	1.62	1.62	0.82	1.38
Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	110	87	82	80	92	70	77	90
Stress to Gelcoat Failure (MPa)	87	49	65	64	80	48	54	80

TABLE 4 THE EFFECT OF LAMINATE CONSTRUCTION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF THIN CHEMICALLY-RESISTANT GELCOATS (FLOWCOATS)

Gelcoat Thickness \approx 0.5mmBack-up System Reinforcement: 4 x 450 g/m² CSM. 30% glass by wt.

Ratio of Bisphenol to Flexible Resin	100:0	90:10	80:20	70:30
Property				
Heat Deflection Temperature (°C)	117	99	83	66
Tensile Strength (MPa)	74	72	61	46
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	3.4	3.4	2.9	2.3
Tensile Elongation to Failure (%)	3.8	4.2	4.5	7.6
Barcol Hardness	36	35	32	31

TABLE 5 THE EFFECT OF FLEXIBILISING RESIN ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CAST BISPHENOL RESIN

Cure: 2% low reactivity MEKP + 6% of a 1% Cobalt solution.